

Pereskiopsis diguetii subsp. *spathulata* stat. nov. (Cactaceae: Opuntioideae)

MAARTEN H. J. VAN DER MEER¹

Abstract—The combination *Pereskiopsis diguetii* subsp. *spathulata* is proposed.

Pereskiopsis spathulata (Otto ex Pfeiff.) Britton & Rose, widely grown by cactus enthusiasts as a grafting stock for tender seedlings, is considered by recent authors to be conspecific with *Pereskiopsis diguetii* (F.A.C.Weber) Britton & Rose and not recognized at any rank (Hunt, Taylor & Charles 2006; Lodé 2015). It is proposed here to recognize it at the rank of subspecies:

***Pereskiopsis diguetii* subsp. *spathulata* (Otto ex Pfeiff.) M.van der Meer stat. nov.**

≡ *Pereskia spathulata* Otto ex Pfeiff.

Enum. Diagn. Cact. 176. (1837)

≡ *Pereskiopsis spathulata* (Otto ex Pfeiff.) Britton & Rose

Smithsonian Misc. Collect. 50: 333 (1907)

Literature

Hunt, D., Taylor, N., & Charles, G. (2006). The New Cactus Lexicon. dh books. Milborne Port, UK.

Lodé, J. (2015). Taxonomy of the Cactaceae: A New Classification of Cacti Based on Molecular Research and Fully Explained.

¹ Roggekamp 379
NL-2592 VV Den Haag
m@vdm.nu
ORCID: 0000-0002-5182-9615